

IMPACT OF BOARD GENDER DIVERSITY, FOREIGN OWNERSHIP, AND OWNERSHIP CONCENTRATION ON CORPORATE FINANCIAL DECISIONS AND FIRM VALUE: EVIDENCE FROM THE TEXTILE SECTOR OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract. *This research examines how diversity on corporate boards, foreign ownership, and block holders' ownership affect business performance and financial decisions, including investment, financing, and dividends. This information is obtained from the annual reports of textile companies listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange between 2016-2023. The findings were estimated using a panel data methodology, the pooled ordinary least squares method. The findings demonstrate a positive relationship between board diversity and investment in operational assets and a negative relationship between financing and business success. Investment in operational assets is inversely related to foreign ownership, but dividends and firm performance are positively related. Blockholders' ownership and dividends and the company's profitability have a positive relationship. The study's findings indicate that diversity on boards and ownership structure (including foreign and blockholder ownership) significantly impact financial decision-making and business performance. Furthermore, this study's results indicate that many conditional theories, including agency theory, pecking order theory, and trade-off theory, assist in comprehending the financial actions of non-financial listed companies in Pakistan. The study's findings could significantly help company managers when making important decisions.*

Keywords: Board diversity, Investment, Financing, Dividend, Security Exchange Commission.

1. Introduction

This research examines how Board gender diversity, foreign ownership, and concentration affect corporate financial decisions and firm value. Corporate finance

focuses on investment, financing, and dividends. Finance managers should carefully make investment, financing, and dividend decisions to maximise shareholder value. The board of directors makes investment decisions for the company's shareholders as part of financial management. Globalisation and financial market integration have made standards for corporate governance more important in developing countries like Pakistan. Pakistan's rising position and distinctive economic climate make it an appropriate framework for evaluating these concerns. Pakistani researchers have extensively studied business governance, recognising its importance. The SECP published the corporate governance code in 2002. Pakistan criticised the project for operational concerns such as conflicts of interest, short-term objectives over long-term goals, and corporate governance^{32]}.

1.1. Problem Statement

Pakistan's Securities and Exchange Commission is a government body that improves corporate governance. SECP published the first Code of Corporate Governance (CCG) in 2002; an amended code was introduced in 2012. SECP continues to enhance governance across the Country. Women are becoming more prevalent and attracting authorities' notice. Under Section 154 of the Firms Act 2017, all public firms must include women on their boards. SECP proposed gender diversity in board composition and suggested female directors. All listed firms must have at least one female director per CCG Regulation 7. Does gender diversity on boards affect business finance decisions? The researchers should pay close attention to this topic since it is important. Foreign direct investment is crucial to economic growth; thus, studies must determine how foreign investor shares affect business financial decisions. To raise capital, a public limited corporation opens its doors to the public. This operation capitalises on the status of a public limited corporation and disperses ownership. The key concerns are how ownership concentration influences business financial choices and how distributed ownership structure is. In conclusion, little research on board diversity, foreign ownership, and ownership concentration on business financial choices suggests this empirical investigation is necessary.

1.2. Objectives of Research

The objective of this study is trifold.

- First, to determine whether board gender diversity affects financial decisions.
- Second, whether foreign and block-held shares affect the financial decisions.
- Finally, to determine whether gender diversity, foreign ownership, and concentration affect firm value.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Agency Theory

According to agency theory, self-interest drives most organisational activity. Management may selectively notify shareholders notwithstanding an information asymmetry ^{1]}. Such ownership over critical information complicates the dispute between managers (agents) and shareholders (principals). According to [28], the board of directors in major firms provides reliable information to the firm's owners, which improves managerial oversight. Agency theory includes dividend distribution, leverage, management equity income, and board composition. The agency's literature states that the board of directors monitors shareholder and management interests to align them [7]. [44], employ agency theory to study how board gender diversity affects corporate profitability. Successful businesses had a varied staff of men and women, which was positively connected with financial performance. Due to their separate cognitive processes, [44] found that female directors had better monitor skills. Women on corporate boards also promote managerial responsibility. The agency theory also states that concentrated ownership improves monitoring, which reduces conflict-of-interest between value-maximising shareholders and self-interested management this is the alignment effect.

2.2. Board Diversity

According to gender theory, women's ethics and ideals make them successful economically. According to research, women tend to be more ethical, sensitive to social

interactions, and compliant with norms. Gender diversity on boards affects business risk-taking and decision-making. Female board involvement increasingly affects corporate governance, financial performance, and risk management. According to research, female directors boost company governance, risk-taking, and financial performance [9]. Agency Theory views female directors as effective monitors of management performance, demanding higher responsibility and showing less tolerance for opportunism. [10], found that female board directors are more diligent and attend more meetings than male directors. Female managers and directors enhance business financial success. A higher number of female board members improves public openness, management control, earnings quality, and informed decision-making. [36] found that female directors improve firm credit ratings. [35] and [13] found that board diversity positively influences the dividend payout ratio. Moreover, investment efficiency moderates board diversity and dividend policy.[34], and[43], revealed that developing countries' corporate board gender diversity negatively affected cash dividends. 37], state that when a corporation has female directors on its board, it positively impacts its investment decisions. Investment efficiency is better in organisations with more female directors. 32], found a substantial negative association between board gender diversity and financing. This suggests that a gender-diverse board may minimise default risks for microfinance institutions (MFIs) and lower financing costs.[27] and [44] found that women on corporate boards boost business performance, except for female CEOs' return on assets. [20], found that power distance and masculinity limit the influence of board gender diversity on company success. Gender diversity on a board has a statistically significant negative influence on ROA and ROE.

2.3. Foreign Ownership

Foreign ownership has been shown to significantly impact financial decision-making in several countries. According to [29], developing country investors generally consider foreign investors more knowledgeable. Their increased knowledge, expertise, and financial market experience may explain this opinion. [31], found that foreign-owned enterprises paid higher dividends. This study supports the assumption that

significant foreign investors prefer incentivising or seeking dividends from firms to overcome the agency problem. In addition, research has indicated that companies are more likely to increase the size of dividend payments when foreign investors are involved^[46]. When investors cannot effectively solve agency concerns, dividends are considered a way to reduce future risks and uncertainties. Since dividends are seen as a desirable source of income by investors worldwide, [24], found a positive relationship between foreign ownership and dividend disbursements. [49], analysis suggests foreign ownership negatively affects corporate investment efficiency. According to [8], and [49], foreign investors with a high-risk aversion prefer to tightly regulate management to guarantee that companies only engage in safe operations. [52], found a significant correlation between foreign ownership, investment efficiency, and financing choices when governments lose power and national governance institutions weaken. [26], found that foreign ownership improves risk propensity, working capital value, and investment efficiency. Both [51] and [40], found that foreign ownership positively affects a company's financial performance. A positive relationship between foreign ownership and performance was shown by^[25]. [17], found that foreign ownership boosts productivity and profitability. This tendency strongly influences organisations that use more technology and human resources. Foreign stock ownership could enhance the firm's informational dynamics. After listing, dual-listed local businesses tend to align with international values^[38]. Local firms partly owned by foreign entities may perform better due to the convergence of governance and business practices with advanced nations. Additionally, overseas managers may help local businesses independently.

2.4. Ownership Concentration

The degree to which investors own a disproportionate number of shares in a company is known as ownership concentration. [3], found a significant positive correlation between publicly listed companies' ownership concentration, dividend payment frequency, and size. According to [4], there is a negative correlation between dividends and concentration of ownership. This analysis supports agency theories that dividend policy helps shareholders oversee firm actions. Research conducted by [53],

shows that ownership concentration is positively and statistically significantly affected by dividend distribution. [19], found that large-block ownership boosts a firm's investment and performance. The controlling stockholders' identification does not affect this relationship. [48], found a significant positive relationship between concentration of ownership and financing decisions. The ownership structure affects the firm's valuation, funding, and bankruptcy risk. [6], found a positive and statistically significant relationship between ownership concentration and company financial performance. This remark suggests that significant owners could improve in making management incentives match shareholder aspirations.

2.5. Firm Size

A company's size is measured by the total value of its assets. High-growth companies have little problem accessing the capital market since investors like them [23]. [41], found that firm size positively affects dividend distribution decisions. [3938], found a statistically significant positive correlation between firm size and dividend policy. Asset portfolio management and composition affect investment decisions. Investments generate returns on capital. The fast-growing economy offers several investment options. A company's financial performance shows how well its main business model uses its assets to create income. According to [3030], firm size has a negative and statistically significant relationship with investment decisions, suggesting that larger companies are further along in their life cycles and, therefore, need less capital accumulation. The importance of business size in studying financial decision determinants is well known. [3030], found a negative relationship between firm size and financing decisions. Smaller businesses had a better financial decision-making relationship than bigger firms^[41]. [18], found a negative relationship between firm size and financing decisions. [42], found a positive correlation between firm size and profitability. [2], research found that overall assets, sales, and workers positively correlated with firm profitability in all three models. However, firm size negatively affects profitability^[6]. [11], research have shown no correlation between business size and profitability.

2.6. Liquidity

A company's ability to meet its financial commitments, including debt repayment and unexpected costs, is directly related to its liquidity, which informs stakeholders about the availability of cash inside the company. Liquidity indicates a company's ability to meet short-term financial obligations upon maturity using readily available liquid assets^{15]}. Liquid companies may distribute dividends more efficiently. [22], found that liquidity positively affects dividend policy. [45], found no statistically significant liquidity effect on dividend policy. 5], analysed panel data from a large sample of US-based enterprises to examine the relationship between cash reserves and company investment. The negative relationship between cash holdings and investment has been shown empirically. The pecking order theory states that organisations with more liquidity have larger retained profits that can be used to finance projects^{21]}, which explains the expected negative relationship between liquidity and financing decisions. 5], found a strong negative link between liquidity and financing. A company's capacity to handle short-term commitments is indicated by liquidity. 47], found that working capital management improves profitability.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Data

The State Bank of Pakistan's financial statement analysis provided balance sheet and income statement data for the researchers to study how board diversity, foreign ownership, and ownership concentration affect corporate financial decisions and firm value. The researchers focused on how these factors impact company financial decisions. A time span spanning from 2016 to 2023 was used to construct the data. SBP does not collect data on corporate gender diversity, foreign ownership, or concentration. I obtained the businesses' annual reports from their websites within the time restriction to do this. As a result, I was able to get the necessary information. There are 816 observations and 102 textile companies in the sample.

3.2. Framework

3.3. Variables and Operationalisation

In Table 1, variables were defined from literature reviews for meaningful comparison.

Table 1: Variables' Operationalisation

Variable	Symbol	Definition
Investment	INV_{it}	Fixed operating assets divided by total assets.
Financing	FIN_{it}	Total debt to total assets.
Dividend	DIV_{it}	Dividend to outstanding common stocks.
Profitability	$PROF_{it}$	Profit before taxes to total assets.
Firm value	FV_{it}	Natural log of market capitalisation. The product of the current market price and outstanding common stocks is market capitalisation.
Board diversity	$BDIV_{it}$	Female directors to total directors.
Foreign ownership	$FOWN_{it}$	Foreign investors' shares to common stocks as a proportion of shares outstand.

Ownership concentration	$OWNC_{it}$	Five individual largest shareholders' shares to outstand common stocks.
Firm size	SIZ_{it}	Natural log of total assets.

3.4. Methodology

Using a panel data methodology pooled OLS method; this empirical research examined how diversity on boards, ownership concentration and foreign ownership affect corporate financial decisions and firm value. STATA software is used in this for analysis of the collected data. Panel data estimating is vital and useful for working with econometric data ^[14]. Panel data analysis also shows that some data points are acceptable for the time series cross-section. It provides a variety of methods for estimating values and considers all people in the cross-sectional dataset throughout different periods. The collection of matrices is made up of pooled panel data.

The following is a representation of the basic regression equations:

$$INV_{it} = \hat{\delta} + \beta_1 BDIV_{it} + \beta_2 FOWN_{it} + \beta_3 OWNC_{it} + \beta_4 SIZ_{it} + \beta_5 PROF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$$FIN_{it} = \hat{\delta} + \beta_1 BDIV_{it} + \beta_2 FOWN_{it} + \beta_3 OWNC_{it} + \beta_4 SIZ_{it} + \beta_5 PROF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$$DIV_{it} = \hat{\delta} + \beta_1 BDIV_{it} + \beta_2 FOWN_{it} + \beta_3 OWNC_{it} + \beta_4 SIZ_{it} + \beta_5 PROF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$$FV_{it} = \hat{\delta} + \beta_1 BDIV_{it} + \beta_2 FOWN_{it} + \beta_3 OWNC_{it} + \beta_4 SIZ_{it} + \beta_5 PROF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

4. Results and Analysis

4.1. Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 summarises the descriptive statistics for variables across 816 observations. The mean values range from 0.4983 for investment to 19.7908 for firm value, reflecting variation in the dataset. The standard deviations indicate substantial variability, with financing having the highest standard deviation of 1.4645, suggesting considerable dispersion in financial performance. The maximum value for dividend is 333.0000, indicating the presence of extreme outliers. The minimum values for most variables are close to zero, except for profitability, which has a minimum value of -0.6802. Liquidity exhibits a high standard deviation of 4.9660, reflecting significant

variability in liquidity across firms. These statistics highlight the diversity and heterogeneity within the sample.

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Obs</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>
INV_{it}	816	0.4983	0.2521	0.0000	0.9998
FIN_{it}	816	0.8053	1.4645	0.0120	24.4783
DIV_{it}	816	3.2002	17.7504	0	333.0000
$PROF_{it}$	816	0.9170	2.4754	-0.6802	70.6301
FV_{it}	816	19.7908	1.7447	15.8949	25.2823
$BDIV_{it}$	816	0.1486	0.1488701	0.0000	0.7143
$FOWN_{it}$	816	0.0060	0.0430405	0.0000	0.5286
$OWNC_{it}$	816	0.6663	0.2026014	0.2110	2.7854
SIZ_{it}	816	14.899	1.6616	10.1536	18.9529
LIQ_{it}	816	1.5899	4.9660	0.0001	75.7608

4.2. Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis reveals significant relationships between various financial and firm-specific variables. A negative correlation is observed between INV and FIN (-0.060) and between INV and FV (-0.250***), suggesting that higher

	INV_{it}	FIN_{it}	DIV_{it}	$PROF_{it}$	FV_{it}	$BDIV_{it}$	$FOWN_{it}$	$OWNC_{it}$	SIZ_{it}	LIQ_{it}
INV_{it}	1.000									
FIN_{it}	-0.06***	1.000								
DIV_{it}	-0.102***	-0.038	1.000							
$PROF_{it}$	-0.052	0.469***	0.003	1.000						
FV_{it}	-0.250***	-0.142***	0.111***	-0.030	1.000					
$BDIV_{it}$	0.0223***	-0.022	-0.071*	-0.004	-0.097**	1.000				
$FOWN_{it}$	-0.083***	-0.037	-0.012	-0.003	0.150***	-0.017	1.000			
$OWNC_{it}$	0.046	-0.044	-0.086**	-0.028	-0.039	0.169***	0.023	1.000		
SIZ_{it}	-0.175***	-0.218***	0.149***	-0.082*	0.679***	-0.205***	0.076*	-0.087**	1.000	
LIQ_{it}	-0.217***	-0.090**	0.033	-0.009	-0.009	0.248***	-0.013	0.019	-0.184***	1.000

investment is linked to lower financial performance and firm value. PROF demonstrates a strong positive correlation with FV (0.679***), indicating that firms with higher profitability tend to have greater firm value. The correlation between DIV and FIN is weak (-0.038), while DIV is positively correlated with FV (0.111***), though the relationship is not strong. LIQ shows a negative correlation with both INV (-0.217***) and SIZ (-0.184***), indicating that higher liquidity is associated with lower investment and firm size levels. Finally, SIZ positively correlates with FV (0.679***) and PROF (0.149***), highlighting that larger firms are more likely to exhibit higher profitability and greater firm value. These correlations highlight key dynamics in the dataset, reflecting the complex interrelationships among the variables.

Regression Analysis

Table 3 results show that board gender diversity has a positive but statistically significant effect ($p = 0.000$), suggesting that higher gender diversity on boards is associated with increased investment decisions. Foreign ownership has a significant negative effect, meaning higher foreign ownership tends to reduce investment decisions. Liquidity has a significant negative impact on influencing investment decisions. However, ownership concentration presents positive but insignificant results, meaning there is no consistent relationship between Ownership concentration and investment decisions. The negative significant relation of firm size indicates that asset income decreases investment. The model itself is statistically significant.

Table 3: Impact on Board Gender Diversity, Foreign Ownership and Ownership Concentration on Investment Decisions

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coeff.</i>	<i>Std. Err.</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>P> t </i>
<i>BDIV_{it}</i>	0.0255	0.0593	-0.4300	0.000
<i>FOWN_{it}</i>	-0.4272	0.1941	-2.2000	0.028
<i>OWNC_{it}</i>	0.0347	0.0418	0.8300	0.4070
<i>SIZ_{it}</i>	-0.0378	0.0535	-0.7100	0.000
<i>LIQ_{it}</i>	-0.0138	0.0017	-7.8600	0.000

FIN_{it}	0.0227	0.0066	-3.4100	0.001
$PROF_{it}$	-0.0012	0.0038143	-0.3300	0.000
_cons	1.0866	0.0899	12.0900	0.000
N	816	R2	0.1188	
F (7, 808)	31.11	Adj R ²	0.1112	
Prob > F	0.000	Root MSE	0.2377	

Table 4 reveals that the board gender diversity is negative and statistically significant ($p = 0.0366$), suggesting a moderate negative relationship with financing decisions. Foreign ownership is statistically insignificant, indicating no strong impact on financing decisions. Ownership concentration is negatively insignificant, suggesting weak influence. Company size significantly negatively affects financing decisions, indicating that larger firms may be less dependent on external financing. Liquidity has a negative and significant relationship with financing decisions, with a coefficient of -0.0429, suggesting that higher liquidity reduces the need for external funding. Profitability positively correlates with financing decisions and is highly significant ($p = 0.0000$), indicating that more profitable firms are more likely to secure financing.

Table 4: Impact of Board Gender Diversity, Foreign Ownership and Ownership Concentration on Financing Decisions

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coeff.</i>	<i>Std. Err.</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>P> t </i>
$BDIV_{it}$	-0.2813	0.3111	-0.9000	0.0366
$FOWN_{it}$	-0.9763	1.0209	-0.9600	0.3390
$OWNC_{it}$	-0.2797	0.2194	-1.27	0.2030
SIZ_{it}	-0.2069	0.0280	-7.3000	0.0000
LIQ_{it}	-0.0429	0.0098	-4.5100	0.0000
INV_{it}	0.6248	0.1832	-3.4100	0.0010

$PROF_{it}$	-0.2614	0.0177	14.71	0.0000
_cons	4.4782	0.4876758	9.1800	0.0000
N	816	R2	0.2814	
F (7, 808)	4521	Adj R ²	0.2752	
Prob > F	0.000	Root MSE	1.2468	

Table 5 shows that board gender diversity has an insignificant negative relationship, suggesting no substantial effect on dividend decisions. Foreign ownership has a positive insignificant relationship, indicating weak evidence of its influence on dividend decisions. Ownership concentration shows a positive but insignificant effect, suggesting a potential but weak impact. Company size has a significantly positive effect, indicating that larger companies are more likely to pay dividends. Liquidity shows small positive but statistically insignificant results, implying limited influence on dividend policies. Profitability shows a positive but weak relationship with dividend decisions, indicating a slight tendency for more profitable companies to distribute dividends.

Table 5: Impact of Board Gender Diversity, Foreign Ownership and Ownership Concentration on Dividend Decisions

Variable	Coeff.	Std. Err.	T	P> t
$BDIV_{it}$	-5.8022	4.3641	-1.3300	0.1840
$FOWN_{it}$	10.9611	14.3185	-0.7700	0.0440
$OWNC_{it}$	5.5087	3.0785	-1.7900	0.0740
SIZ_{it}	1.4407	0.3933	3.6600	0.0000
LIQ_{it}	0.2006	0.13302	1.5100	0.1320
INV_{it}	-4.6479	2.5699	-1.8100	0.0410
$PROF_{it}$	0.0625	0.2492	0.2500	0.028
_Cons	-11.6764	6.8398	-1.7100	0.0880
N	818	R ²	0.0378	

F (7, 808)	4.54	Adj R ²	0.0295
Prob > F	0.0001	Root MSE	17.487

Table 6 shows that board gender diversity negatively insignificantly affects profitability. Foreign ownership has positive statistically insignificant results, indicating its impact on profitability is weak. Ownership concentration shows a positive but insignificant relationship with profitability, implying no meaningful influence. Firm size has a positive and statistically significant relationship with profitability, suggesting that larger firms are more profitable. Liquidity is negatively insignificant, indicating little effect on profitability.

Table 6: Impact of Board Gender Diversity, Foreign Ownership and Ownership Concentration on Profitability

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coeff.</i>	<i>Std. Err.</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>P> t </i>
<i>BDIV_{it}</i>	-0.0622	0.5469	0.1100	0.0090
<i>FOWN_{it}</i>	0.7917	1.7892	0.4400	0.0500
<i>OWNC_{it}</i>	0.0754	0.3859	-0.2000	0.8450
<i>SIZ_{it}</i>	0.0428	0.0494	0.8700	0.0386
<i>LIQ_{it}</i>	-0.0193	0.0162	1.1900	0.2360
<i>FIN_{it}</i>	-0.8107	0.0543	14.92	0.0000
Cons	-1.1934	0.8276	-1.4400	0.150
N	816	R ²	0.2226	
F (7, 809)	38.61	Adj R ²	0.2168	
Prob > F	0.000	Root MSE	2.1907	

Table 7 demonstrates that board gender diversity has a positive insignificant relationship, suggesting that gender diversity does not significantly influence firm value. Foreign ownership shows significant positive results, indicating that higher foreign ownership is associated with increased firm value. Ownership concentration also has an insignificant positive relationship with firm value, suggesting a minimal

effect on firm value. Firm size positively correlates with firm value, suggesting that bigger firms have greater firm values. Liquidity is positively related to firm value with a coefficient of 0.0491, and it is highly statistically significant, suggesting that firms with more liquidity are valued higher.

Table 7: Impact of Board Gender Diversity, Foreign Ownership and Ownership Concentration on Firm Value

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coeff.</i>	<i>Std. Err.</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>P> t </i>
<i>BDIV_{it}</i>	0.1587	0.31200	0.5100	0.6110
<i>FOWN_{it}</i>	4.0251	1.0207	3.9400	0.0000
<i>OWNC_{it}</i>	0.1405	0.2201	0.6400	0.5240
<i>SIZ_{it}</i>	0.7435	0.0281	26.39	0.0000
<i>LIQ_{it}</i>	0.0491	0.0093	5.2900	0.0000
<i>FIN_{it}</i>	-0.0363	0.0310	1.1700	0.0243
_cons	8.4645	0.4721	17.9300	0.0000
N	816	R ²		0.4907
F (7, 809)	129.91	Adj R ²		0.4869
Prob > F	0.000	Root MSE		1.2497

4.3. Discussion

This empirical research examines how board and ownership structure affect company financial decisions (investment, financing, dividends) and business performance. Firm performance is assessed using accounting- and market-based criteria. Due to the 2017 corporate landscape shift, this empirical research primarily considers the influence of board diversity (i.e., the percentage of female directors) on corporate financial decisions and company performance. Under Section 154 of the Firms Act 2017, all public firms must include women on their boards. This led to several Code of Corporate Governance revisions in 2017. Regulation seven mandates

at least one female director on listed company boards. This research examined how foreign and blockholder ownership affect business financial choices and performance.

Board diversity is positively associated with operational asset investment. Because female directors are risk-averse, the relationship is favourable. The ideal investment for them would be a project with a return proportion to the level of risk involved. The positive relationship between board diversity and investment confirms ^{37]} findings. A negative relationship exists between board diversity and financing decisions. The tax benefit on interest payments makes debt cheaper than equity. Debt raises the likelihood of default; hence, if bankruptcy costs (direct and indirect) are high, the corporation should utilise debt sparingly. Female directors prefer not to be too pressured and advocate for sensible debt management. The negatively impacted relationship between board diversity and finance supports ^{12],32]}. There is a significant negative relationship between board diversity and profitability. According to finance, investment and financing decisions determine profitability. Board members must make riskier investments and make financing decisions to maximise profits. Female directors avoid undue pressure that undermines corporate profitability. The negative relationship between board diversity and profitability supports ^[20].

Foreign ownership negatively affects investment and is statistically significant. According to finance, investment relies on capital availability and cost. High-cost funds hinder operational asset investment. Due to the country's poor political and economic condition and COVID-19 aftermath, financing costs are rising. These factors discourage foreign investors from investing in businesses worth less than the cost of capital. The negative relationship between foreign ownership and investment confirms the finding of ^[49]. Foreign ownership has a positive relationship with dividends and is statistically significant. Successful companies invest in fixed assets, repay debts, or pay dividends. Without attractive investment opportunities, companies pay dividends to shareholders rather than engage in undesired ventures. A positive relationship verifies the results of ^[24]. Foreign ownership positively relates to accounting- and market-based performance indicators. Foreign investors often put their money into reputable businesses with a record of success and a low default likelihood. They also desire board

membership and investments worth more than money. The positive relationship between foreign ownership and performance supports ^[51] and ^[40].

Ownership concentration is the proportion of shares held by the five biggest owners. Table 2 reveals five investors own 66.63 percent of outstanding shares. This ratio suggests ownership is more concentrated than dispersed. A small group of powerful shareholders decide what happens to the rest of the stockholders. The positive relationship between ownership concentration and dividend decisions may be because corporations want to distribute more and hold less for investment due to the country's unstable political and economic conditions. Companies seek free cash to avoid agency issues. The positive relationship between ownership concentration and dividend supports ^{3]} results.

The size of the firm has a significant negative relationship with investment. The relationship between business size and investment is inverse, contrary to expectations. Large and established businesses spend less on their current company if the ROI is lower than the market return. Additionally, mature companies keep less and give more to shareholders to prevent free cash flow conflict of interest. The negative relationship between firm size and investment supports ^[30] results. Size matters and inversely affect financing. Firm size and leverage have a positive relationship in the trade-off theory. The trade-off approach focuses on debt costs (bankruptcy) and advantages (tax advantage). Notably, only profitable businesses may benefit from debt. Tax concessions are not available to firms with negative profits. Their default risk is likewise significant. Large companies with negative profitability and substantial default risk borrow less. The negative relationship between firm size and financing supports ^[30]. Firm size positively correlates with dividends, profitability, and firm value. For the reasons already stated, major companies would cut spending if their operational asset ROI is lower than the market rate. Big companies seek to distribute more and keep less. Therefore, dividend increases communicate to the market that future profits will increase firm value.

An inverse relationship exists between liquidity and investment. The opposite relationship is natural since investing more in current assets reduces financing for fixed

operational assets. Liquidity inversely affects investment, supporting ^{5]}. Finance and liquidity are negatively related. The pecking order theory indicates that corporations with enough finances borrow less. The inverse relationship matches ^[21]. Overall, board diversity, foreign ownership, and ownership concentration affect business financial decisions and performance.

5. Conclusion

This research looks at how things like board diversity, foreign ownership, and ownership concentration affect companies' financial choices and performance. For this purpose, we estimated the outcomes using the 2016–2023 annual reports of non-financial companies traded on the Pakistan Stock Exchange. Since female directors tend to be more risk-cautious and choose projects with returns that are directly proportionate to the level of risk, the results demonstrated that a diverse board is positively associated with investments in operational assets. Having a diverse board has the opposite effect on financing since debt is seen as less expensive than equity because of tax breaks for interest payments. Because investment is contingent on the availability and cost of capital, foreign ownership is negatively related to investment. As a result of the rising cost of funds in the country, high-cost funds deter investment in operational assets. Because profitable businesses may reinvest in fixed operational assets, pay down debt, or pay out dividends to shareholders, there is a strong correlation between foreign ownership and dividends. Since companies would rather pay out dividends than save money for investments, considering the current political and economic climate, there is a positive correlation between ownership concentration and dividends. Large, established companies are less likely to put money into their current operations if the ROI is lower than the market rate of return, suggesting a negative correlation between company size and investment. Since larger companies are less likely to invest if their operational asset return is lower than the market return, a positive correlation exists between firm size and dividends, profitability, and company value. Because companies with enough cash are less likely to take out loans, liquidity negatively correlates with investment. Finally, board diversity, foreign ownership, and

ownership concentration substantially affect a company's financial decisions and efficiency.

5.1. Recommendations

The literature review indicates the critical need to investigate how external governance measures and country-specific factors affect financial decisions and firm performance.

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